

DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER SCIENCE

TDT4501 - SPECIALIZATION PROJECT

Aspect Based Sentiment Analysis in Municipality Documents

Author:
Sebastian Småland

Supervisor:
Benjamin Uwe Kille

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Abstract

Oslo Municipality seeks to automate the extraction of public opinion from large volumes of unstructured hearing documents to enhance data-driven decision-making in urban development. While the municipality's "AI Factory" initiative has successfully implemented summarization tools, these fail to provide the structured, quantitative data required to measure the distribution of support and opposition across policy topics. This project investigates the feasibility of implementing Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) to bridge this gap within the constraints of a low-resource, privacy-sensitive public sector environment.

Through a Structured Literature Review ($N = 26$), this study maps the transition in the state-of-the-art from discriminative classifiers to Generative AI and structure-aware architectures. Concurrently, an Exploratory Data Analysis on a pilot dataset of municipal texts ($N = 63$) identifies a critical "Span Ambiguity Gap": while human annotators struggle to agree on exact text boundaries for bureaucratic phrases ($\kappa = 0.21$), they exhibit high reliability in identifying semantic categories ($\kappa = 0.93$).

These findings demonstrate that standard extraction pipelines are allegedly ill-suited for the bureaucratic register. Consequently, this report proposes a strategic pivot to Aspect Category Sentiment Analysis (ACSA). The study concludes with a proposal for a subsequent Master's Thesis centered on a Teacher-Student framework, which utilizes Large Language Models (LLMs) to generate synthetic training data ("Inverse Generation"). This approach aims to enable the training of capable, privacy-compliant local models, effectively solving the "Cold Start" data scarcity problem while bypassing the inherent ambiguity of manual span annotation.

Preface

This work is written as a preparatory project for the subject TDT4501 - Computer Science, Specialization Project in Autumn 2025. I would like to thank my supervisor, Benjamin Kille, for his unwavering belief that this project isn't completely dumbfounded from the get-go. I would also like to thank my contacts at Utviklings- og Kompetanseetaten (UKE), namely Pål Enger and Jonas Hildershavn. Settling together with UKE on an actual research goal/thesis somewhat late in early October, this project may suffer from an unreasonable dose of pessimism related to my thoughts on whether the overall research goal is attainable and useful. My hopes are that I'm not woefully correct, as the work done this semester and the next hopefully amounts to something tangible and beneficial for Oslo Municipality by the end of my thesis.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Oslo Municipality is currently advancing its digital infrastructure through the establishment of an **AI Competence Center** and the corresponding “**AI Factory**”—a standardized framework designed to deploy modular artificial intelligence solutions across the municipality’s agencies. While the AI Factory has successfully operationalized modules for tasks such as speech-to-text, document anonymization, and general text summarization, the domain of urban development presents unique challenges that these general-purpose tools cannot fully address.

Municipal building-permit and urban-development processes involve a large number of stakeholders, extensive documentation, and intricate exchanges of opinion. The Municipality seeks to gain systematic insight into the specific topics or aspects toward which different actors express support or opposition. Currently, this process relies on labor-intensive manual assessment or simple LLM-based summarization. While summarization provides a useful qualitative overview, it fails to capture the *quantitative distribution* of public opinion required for data-driven decision-making.

To close this gap in the AI Factory’s capabilities, there is a distinct requirement for analytical methods capable of reliably identifying (i) which aspects are under discussion, (ii) the nature and polarity of the attitude expressed, and (iii) the actor or stakeholder by whom that attitude is voiced.

1.2 Problem Context: The Challenge of Municipal Text

The transition from general summarization to precise quantitative analysis represents a directional change in relation to the municipality’s general AI strategy: from *generating text* to *extracting structured data*. However, automating this process is non-trivial due to the specific linguistic and structural characteristics of the public sector domain.

Analyzing public hearing documents presents distinct challenges compared to standard consumer reviews. Unlike the concise, explicit feedback found in product reviews (e.g., “The battery life is poor”), municipal texts are characterized by their bureaucratic terminology, structural complexity, and reliance on implicit argumentation. These characteristics create a significant *domain shift*: the phenomenon where machine learning (ML) models, specifically for natural language processing (NLP), trained on general corpora perform poorly on specialized texts due to differences in vocabulary and distribution (Pan and Q. Yang 2010).

1.2.1 Unstructured Data and Knowledge Mining

Public hearings generate massive volumes of unstructured data, with submissions arriving mostly as PDFs, emails, and scanned letters that often lack metadata regarding the sender’s stance. Current workflows in the sector typically rely on manual reading or simple LLM summarization. However, summarization alone is insufficient for decision-making; while it provides a qualitative overview, it fails to generate the structured, quantitative data required for statistical analysis.

This challenge represents a bottleneck in automated knowledge mining (Hearst 1999). Transforming unstructured text into structured information is resource-intensive but essential for extracting high-quality insights from large corpora. Unlike standard phrase mining, which relies on statistical frequency, mining municipal documents requires context-aware methods to filter noise and retain the structural integrity of arguments (X. Zhang et al. 2021).

1.2.2 Terminology and Bureaucratic Register

The language used in hearing documents is formal, indirect, and highly domain-specific, aligning with challenges identified in specialized domains like Legal NLP, where jargon and complex language pose significant hurdles for general-purpose models (Quevedo et al. 2024). Attitudinal stances are frequently articulated through “bureaucratic circumlocution”—using many words to express a simple objection politely.

This complexity is compounded by semantic ambiguity. Models often struggle to determine stance when polarity is not explicitly stated. In municipal texts, a phrase like “We request a review of the shadow analysis” appears neutral on the surface but functionally serves as a negative objection. Standard emotion lexicons (which are used in other, less opaque domains) often fail to capture these domain-specific linguistic markers.

1.2.3 The Challenge of Implicit Sentiment

Perhaps the most significant barrier is that sentiment in this domain is predominantly implicit. This aligns with the problem of *Implicit Aspect Detection* in Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) (Soni and Rambola 2022). While most research focuses on explicit aspects (words physically present in the text with an “obvious” directed affection), a significant percentage of real-world opinions target implicit aspects insinuated by context. Detecting the polarity of such statements requires a model capable of inferring the target and the stance without relying on explicit sentiment adjectives.

1.3 Project Description

This pre-project investigates the application of aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA) and stance detection to Norwegian municipal documents originating from building-permit and urban-development processes. Particular emphasis is placed on evaluating methods grounded in contemporary transformer-based architectures and large language models (LLMs), as well as on assessing the feasibility of establishing an annotated ground-truth corpus to support subsequent research or the development of production-grade systems.

1.4 Objective

The objective is to map the current scientific state of the art in aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA) and stance detection methods, and to evaluate their applicability to complex, formal Norwegian-language documents.

1.5 Research Questions

- **RQ1 - Method Landscape:** What are the state-of-the-art methods for extracting aspects and stance from complex, domain-specific documents, and how do these methods perform in the context of Norwegian municipal text?
- **RQ2 - Ground Truth Construction:** How can we engineer a consistent annotation schema (ontology) for urban development aspects that maximizes annotation reliability/consistency in Norwegian municipal texts?
- **RQ3 - Practical Feasibility:** To what extent can Generative ABSA (e.g., sequence-to-sequence generation) outperform standard classification baselines (e.g., BERT-based) in extracting complex (Aspect, Stance, Actor) triplets from long-form documents?

1.6 Constraints

This project operates within specific theoretical and operational boundaries designed to ensure feasibility within the specialization project timeframe.

- **Linguistic Scope:** The study focuses exclusively on Norwegian municipal administrative text. While the municipality receives input in various languages and dialects (including Nynorsk), the primary analysis targets standard Norwegian Bokmål and the specific "bureaucratic register" defined in Section 1.2.2.
- **Annotation Granularity:** Based on preliminary findings regarding boundary ambiguity (detailed in Chapter 4), this project constrains the analytical scope to *Aspect Category Sentiment Analysis* (ACSA). The extraction of precise text spans (Aspect Term Extraction) is treated as a secondary interpretability feature rather than a primary classification metric.
- **Data Privacy and Access:** To comply with GDPR and municipal data handling guidelines, the project utilizes publicly available hearing documents provided by the Agency for Planning and Building. No Personally Identifiable Information (PII) is processed (although it is available within the data source used for the pilot analysis), and thus we do not concern ourselves with models restricted to those deployable within compliant environments (e.g., local sovereign models or enterprise-grade APIs with zero-retention policies).
- **Computational Resources:** Experiments are constrained by the available computational budget typical of a master's thesis. To this end, the project prioritizes *Label-Efficient* and *Parameter-Efficient* methods (such as prompting and low-rank adaptation) over the resource-intensive pre-training of new large language models from scratch.

1.7 Thesis Outline

The remainder of this report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2: Background** establishes the theoretical foundations of Sentiment Analysis, the Transformer architecture, and the current landscape of Norwegian Language Models.
- **Chapter 3: Related Work** analyzes the specific research gaps associated with applying NLP to the public sector, specifically focusing on data scarcity, linguistic heterogeneity, and the limitations of cross-lingual transfer.
- **Chapter 4: Exploratory Data Analysis** presents a pilot study on $N = 63$ municipal hearing sentences. This chapter provides empirical evidence for the "Span Ambiguity" problem, motivating the methodological pivot to category-based analysis.
- **Chapter 5: Methodology** outlines the protocol for the Structured Literature Review (SLR) conducted to identify state-of-the-art architectures for this domain.
- **Chapter 6: Results** presents the findings of the SLR, categorizing the dominant approaches into Generative, Structure-Aware, and Domain-Adaptive methods.
- **Chapter 7: Analysis and Discussion** synthesizes the findings from the literature and the pilot study to propose a theoretically grounded architecture for Oslo Municipality's "AI Factory."
- **Chapter 8: Conclusion and Future Work** summarizes the contributions and outlines the experimental plan for the subsequent Master's Thesis.

2 Background

2.1 Foundations of Sentiment Analysis

Sentiment Analysis (SA), often synonymous with Opinion Mining, is the computational study of opinions, sentiments, evaluations, and emotions expressed in text. The field has evolved through distinct stages of granularity, driven by the increasing need for precision in extracting user intent. Its foundational research focused on distinguishing between factual (objective) and opinionated (subjective) language, a necessary precursor to classification (Wiebe et al. 1999).

In its earliest forms, Sentiment Analysis treated text as a single unit. Document-level SA classifies an entire document as generally positive or negative (Pang, Lee and Vaithyanathan 2002; Turney 2002). While effective for short, uniform texts, this approach relies on the assumption that a document discusses a single topic with a consistent polarity. Sentence-level SA increased granularity, but still struggled with sentences containing contrasting opinions (e.g., *"The plan looks good, but the cost is too high"*).

The critical pivot in the field occurred when researchers recognized that users often express mixed sentiments toward different attributes of the same entity. M. Hu and Liu 2004 introduced "Feature-based opinion mining," which proposed mining specific product features (now called "aspects") and determining sentiment for each. This concept was formalized as Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA), a major development further defined and standardized largely through the SemEval shared tasks (Pontiki et al. 2014). For complex documents with differing opinions on a per-sentence basis, this evolution is critical; traditional document-level analysis would average conflicting signals into a "Neutral" score, obscuring the very conflicts that are still valid when considering the affected object as an item of different, but likewise important attributes.

2.1.1 NLP and NLU Context

Sentiment Analysis is a subfield of Natural Language Processing (NLP), situated at the intersection of computer science, artificial intelligence, and linguistics. While NLP encompasses any computational manipulation of text, Sentiment Analysis specifically falls under Natural Language Understanding (NLU). NLU focuses on machine reading comprehension; getting a computer to comprehend the meaning and intent behind words, rather than just processing their syntax (Pang and Lee 2008). A standard Information Retrieval system can find documents containing the word "noise," but an NLU system determines whether the "noise" is being discussed as a problem (Negative) or a mitigated issue (Positive).

2.2 Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis

Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) represents a granular refinement of opinion mining that moves beyond document-level classification to capture the nuanced relationships between specific entities and the sentiments expressed toward them (Liu 2012). Formally, the goal of ABSA is to extract a set of aspect-sentiment pairs from a given sentence. In its most complete form, often and more recently termed Aspect Sentiment Quad Prediction (ASQP), this involves identifying a quadruplet: (c, a, o, p) , where c is the Aspect Category, a is the Aspect Term, o is the Opinion Term, and p is the Sentiment Polarity (W. Zhang et al. 2021).

This structural decomposition addresses the "Mixed Sentiment" problem inherent in multi-faceted feedback, where a single submission often supports specific technical details while opposing broader reaching impacts.

2.2.1 Taxonomy of ABSA Tasks

The field divides this objective into several distinct sub-tasks, ranging from simple classification to complex sequence generation (Liu 2012). The structure and standardized datasets for these tasks were first formalized through the SemEval shared tasks (Pontiki et al. 2014).

Aspect Term Extraction (ATE) is formulated as a sequence labeling task. Given a sequence of tokens, the model must predict a label sequence to identify the boundaries of aspect terms. Recent work unifies this task with others via a generative sequence-to-sequence framework (Yan et al. 2021).

Aspect Sentiment Classification (ASC) is a classification task conditioned on the aspect term. Given a sentence and a specified aspect term, the model computes the probability distribution over polarities (Tang et al. 2016). This is essential for determining if a mention of “shadows” is descriptive (Neutral) or a complaint (Negative).

Aspect Category Detection (ACD) is a multi-label classification problem. Unlike ATE, which extracts words present in the text, ACD maps the text to a predefined ontology of categories (e.g., *Economics, Safety*), even if the category name never appears in the text.

2.2.2 Aspect Category Sentiment Analysis (ACSA)

This project will attempt to argue for a focus on **Aspect Category Sentiment Analysis (ACSA)**, which is the intersection of ACD and ASC:

$$f(X) \rightarrow \{(c, p) \mid c \in C, p \in P\}$$

In ACSA, the system identifies the sentiment p directed at a category c , without necessarily requiring the extraction of an explicit aspect term a . The standardized approach to this category-based classification was also defined through shared tasks like SemEval-2014 (Pontiki et al. 2014). This formulation may have the property of being strictly more robust for domains characterized by implicit sentiment and bureaucratic circumlocution. By targeting the *category* rather than the *span term*, ACSA bypasses the boundary ambiguity of the aspect term while preserving the analytical value for decision-makers.

2.3 Overview of Architectures

The field of Natural Language Processing has evolved through three distinct paradigms, each addressing the limitations of its predecessor. This project relies on the third paradigm: Pre-trained Language Models based on the Transformer architecture, which represents the current state-of-the-art for handling complex, long-context documents.

2.3.1 From Feature Engineering to Deep Learning

Rule-Based and Traditional ML: Early systems relied on handcrafted features, sentiment lexicons (static dictionaries of positive/negative words), and linear classifiers like Support Vector Machines (SVM). While interpretable and surely more explainable, these systems struggled with context, sarcasm, and domain adaptation, due to the way they treated words as independent units (“Bag of Words”) rather than cohesive sequences.

The Deep Learning Wave (RNNs/LSTMs): The introduction of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and Long Short-Term Memory networks (LSTMs) marked a significant shift. LSTMs were specifically designed to address the vanishing gradient problem (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber 1997), allowing them to retain information over much longer sequences than traditional RNNs. While these sequential models capture local context better than SVMs, for longer and more complex documents, their inability to model extremely long-range dependencies was still a critical failure point whenever the wording got more intricate in a document.

2.3.2 The Transformer Architecture

The introduction of the **Transformer** architecture by Vaswani et al. 2017 revolutionized the field by abandoning sequential processing in its then current form. Instead of reading left-to-right, Transformers utilize a **Self-Attention** mechanism that allows the model to weigh the importance of every word in a sequence relative to every other word, simultaneously.

The Mechanism of Self-Attention: The core innovation that enables this parallel processing is Scaled Dot-Product Attention. Mathematically, the model maps input embeddings into three vectors: a Query (Q), a Key (K), and a Value (V). The attention score is calculated as:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (1)$$

Where d_k is the dimension of the key vectors, acting as a scaling factor to stabilize gradients. Intuitively, this mechanism functions like a differentiable retrieval system.

2.3.3 Encoder vs. Decoder Models

While the original Transformer (Vaswani et al. 2017) contained both an Encoder and a Decoder, modern NLP models typically specialize in one stack:

- **Encoder-Only Models (e.g., BERT, NorBERT):** These utilize bidirectional attention to “see” the entire sentence simultaneously (Devlin et al. 2019). They create rich contextual embeddings, making them the industry standard for discriminative tasks like classification (ASC).
- **Decoder-Only Models (e.g., GPT-4, Llama, Gemini):** These employ **causal masking** to predict the next token in a sequence, following the paradigm established by models like GPT (Radford and Narasimhan 2018). While historically less precise at classification, their massive parameter scale (significantly expanded after ChatGPT popularized the technology (OpenAI 2022)) allows them to perform complex Generative ABSA by generating structured output directly from a prompt.

2.4 From Fine-Tuning to Prompting

The shift to Decoder-only architectures has introduced a new paradigm in NLP: the transition from *Fine-Tuning* to *Prompting*. Fine tuning is the classical method of training the pre-trained model even further on specific, smaller datasets for a downstream task, resulting in updates to the model’s weights. However, as mentioned by E. J. Hu et al. 2021 and Ding et al. 2023, memory and computational costs become infeasible due to regular major model updates and loss of important aspects like inference speed. In opposition to this is the focus on prompting as the favorable way to increase output quality and the ability to follow increasingly complex instructions.

2.4.1 Instruction Tuning

While pre-training teaches a model statistical language properties, **Instruction Tuning** aligns the model with user intent by fine-tuning it on (Instruction, Output) pairs (Wei et al. 2022). This enables the model to follow specific schema constraints, such as formatting output as JSON or tuples.

2.4.2 In-Context Learning (Few-Shot Theory)

In-Context Learning (ICL) refers to the ability of Large Language Models to learn a task at inference time without gradient updates (Brown et al. 2020). Unlike standard supervised learning, which maximizes $P(y | x)$ based on updated weights, Few-Shot prompting maximizes $P(y | x, C)$, where C is a context string containing k examples of the task (x_i, y_i) . This mechanism allows for **Few-Shot Learning (FSL)**, where the model infers the task pattern solely from the provided context.

2.5 Synthetic Data Generation

Synthetic Data Generation is a technique where a high-capacity "teacher" model (e.g., GPT-4) generates artificial labeled examples to train a smaller "student" model (e.g. GPT4-mini). Research indicates that this approach allows smaller models to approximate the performance of larger models in scenarios where real-world data is unavailable or privacy-restricted (Li et al. 2023).

2.6 Advancements in Norwegian NLP

The development of Norwegian language technology has followed the global shift toward deep learning, characterized by two main categories of models, as seen before in 2.3.3

2.6.1 The Monolingual Encoder Era

The release of large-scale monolingual models provided the first robust baselines for Norwegian text classification. Specifically, **NorBERT** (Kutuzov et al. 2021) and **NB-BERT** (Kummervold et al. 2021) represent the state-of-the-art for discriminative tasks. These models are BERT-based architectures (Encoder-only) trained on the Norwegian Colossal Corpus (NCC). By training on native text rather than multilingual mixes, they capture syntactic nuances and cultural context, such as the distinction between Bokmål and Nynorsk, which might be missed by the larger, general-purpose models.

2.6.2 Generative Models

The generative landscape for Norwegian is currently divided between:

- **Multilingual LLMs:** Massive models (e.g., GPT-4) with high general reasoning capabilities but lower exposure to specific Norwegian cultural contexts.
- **Sovereign Models:** Initiatives such as **NorLLM** by NorwAI (NorwAI (Norwegian Research Center for AI Innovation) 2023-2024) aim to develop native generative base models (e.g., NorwAI-Mistral-7B; NorwAI et al. 2024) to bridge the gap between cultural understanding and generative capability.

2.7 Chapter Summary

This chapter defined core technologies relevant to the problem statement, which includes the **Transformer architecture** (Section 2.3.2), the **In-Context Learning** paradigm (Section 2.4.2), and the specific landscape of **Norwegian NLP models** (Section 2.6). These definitions provide the theoretical basis for understanding the specific domain challenges, such as data scarcity and linguistic complexity, which are analyzed in the following chapter on Related Work.

3 Related Work and Open Challenges

While the fundamental definitions of Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) and Transformer architectures are well-established (as detailed in Chapter 2), applying these methods to the public sector presents a distinct set of challenges not typically addressed in standard commercial research. This chapter outlines the landscape of domain-specific challenges. For the case of Oslo Municipality’s AI Factory Initiative, it includes specifically data scarcity, linguistic heterogeneity, and the complexity of policy analysis that define the research gap this project addresses.

3.1 The “Cold Start” Problem in Public Administration

Standard supervised learning paradigms require massive annotated datasets to converge. Not only confined to recommender systems and network-based platforms, a defining characteristic of the municipal domain is the “Cold Start” problem: while data volume is high (thousands of PDF pages), labeled ground truth is virtually non-existent for our niche use-case.

As a consequence, the relevant literature for this domain shifts away from the standard supervised methods described in Section 2.3, necessitating *Label-Efficient* paradigms. Hedderich et al. 2021 identifies this lack of annotated data as the primary bottleneck for NLP in low-resource specialized domains. The central debate in this sub-field, which will be explored via the Systematic Literature Review in Chapter 5 and 6 is whether to rely on *Domain-Adaptive Pretraining* (continuing to train models on raw text to learn the domain distribution) or *Generative Data Augmentation* (using LLMs to synthesize training data) to bridge this gap.

3.2 Linguistic Heterogeneity: “Kansellistil” vs. Vernacular

A unique challenge in municipal document analysis is the rather large variance in linguistic style, often referred to as *Linguistic Heterogeneity*. Municipal corpora are not homogeneous; they are comprised of two distinct sub-languages that frequently appear in the same case file:

- **Administrative Language (*Kansellistil*):** Used by the municipality and professional developers. Research in Legal NLP indicates that such text is characterized by passive voice, complex sentence structures, and precise legalistic vocabulary that challenges models trained on general web corpora (Chalkidis et al. 2019).
- **Citizen Vernacular:** Used in public hearing submissions (*høringsinnspill*). This text is often emotional, informal, and may contain dialectal variations or non-standard Norwegian syntax.

Standard NLP research often assumes a consistent register (e.g., all news articles or all product reviews). However, the domain gap between formal regulations and informal citizen feedback requires models capable of parsing bureaucratic circumlocution (e.g., “We request a review of the shadow analysis”) as effectively as explicit complaints, while also not foregoing the task of correctly identifying the less verbose, vernacular writing style.

3.3 The Monolingual vs. Cross-Lingual Debate

For low-resource languages like Norwegian, a central architectural decision in the related work is the choice between **Monolingual** and **Cross-Lingual** models.

- **Translation-Based Transfer:** Early approaches in low-resource settings relied on translating data to English to leverage high-resource models (e.g., BERT-Large). While effective for general topics, Kutuzov et al. 2021 note that translation approaches often fail to capture the

nuance of culturally specific administrative terms (e.g., distinguishing *bruksendring* from simple renovation) or distinct syntactic features of Norwegian variants.

- **Dedicated Norwegian Models:** The release of models like NorBERT and NB-BERT has shifted the focus towards native processing. These models are pre-trained on the Norwegian Colossal Corpus (NCC), capturing syntactic nuances that multilingual models might miss (Kutuzov et al. 2021).

However, a significant gap remains: while native Norwegian models excel at *classification*, they historically lack the *generative* capabilities of massive international models. This project sits at the center of this quandary, evaluating whether prompted multilingual LLMs can outperform smaller, native discriminative models in this specific domain.

3.4 Limitations of Standard ABSA for Policy Analysis

Finally, the transition from commercial reviews to policy analysis requires a fundamental shift in task formulation. Standard ABSA literature frequently treats sentiment as a binary relationship between a specific explicit term and a polarity (e.g., "The battery is bad").

In the context of urban planning, this formulation is often insufficient. Soni and Rambola 2022 argue that in complex domains, a significant percentage of sentiment is insinuated through context, conditional argumentation, or technical objections rather than explicit adjectives. Furthermore, public-sector decision-making is subject to transparency requirements that favor *Explainable ABSA*, where the model must extract the text span serving as evidence. Current research rarely applies these complex tuple extraction methods to long-context administrative documents, representing the primary research gap this thesis seeks to close.

3.5 Summary

This chapter has identified the specific operational challenges that render standard "off-the-shelf" NLP insufficient for Oslo Municipality. The combination of the "Cold Start" data problem (Section 3.1), the complexity of bureaucratic language (Section 3.2), and the prevalence of implicit sentiment (Section 3.4) necessitates a specialized methodological approach. The following chapters detail the Systematic Literature Review conducted to identify architectures capable of addressing these specific gaps.

4 Exploratory Data Analysis

Before defining the final methodology for the expected thesis work, an exploratory analysis was conducted on a pilot dataset to assess the feasibility of strict span extraction as a way to approach quantifiable analysis of sentiments.

4.1 Motivation for Preliminary Testing

To assess the feasibility of automated extraction pipelines for Oslo Municipality, this project builds upon a pilot dataset and preliminary experiments originally conducted by the author in a course: *TDT13 - Advanced Text Analytics and Language Understanding* (Småland 2025). The dataset consists of $N = 63$ opinion-bearing sentences extracted from public consultation statements ("uttalelser") regarding urban development.

4.2 Annotation Reliability

While the dataset remains unchanged, this chapter re-examines the annotation metrics from that preliminary investigation to derive new methodological constraints for the current project. Specifically, we analyze the divergence in *Intra-Annotator Agreement* (notably distinct from the more commonly used *Inter-Annotator Agreement*) to determine the viable granularity for automated sentiment analysis in this domain.

4.3 Span Ambiguity

A critical finding from the preliminary analysis was the significant disparity in annotation reliability across different tasks. When annotating the same data points with a three-week interval, the internal consistency (measured by Cohen's Kappa) varied drastically depending on the task definition:

- **Aspect Categorization:** $\kappa = 0.9351$ (Almost Perfect).
- **Sentiment Polarity:** $\kappa = 0.8752$ (Almost Perfect).
- **Span Extraction (Exact Boundaries):** $\kappa = 0.2132$ (Slight Agreement).

4.3.1 Conclusion of Investigation

The low agreement score for span extraction ($\kappa = 0.21$) is not indicative of annotator error, but rather highlights a specific characteristic of the bureaucratic domain: *Boundary Ambiguity*.

In municipal texts, aspect terms are often embedded in complex compound nouns or diffuse phrasings where the exact boundary of the "aspect" is subjective. As illustrated in Figure 1, an annotator might inconsistently toggle between extracting "height," "building height," or the full phrase "the proposed building height of 24 meters."

Figure 1: Visualizing the ‘Span Ambiguity Gap’ in bureaucratic text. While the textual boundary of the aspect is subjective (Red), the semantic category is unambiguous (Green).

In contrast to the span instability, the high agreement for categorization ($\kappa = 0.93$) demonstrates that the conceptual understanding of the text is stable.

4.4 Feasibility Study Outcomes

As presented in Table 1 (Småland 2025), the ‘Strict Triplet F1’ for Strategy B was extremely low (0.1053). However, when the same model outputs were evaluated using the ACSA metric, the performance increased significantly to 0.5263. This quantitative disparity confirms that the model accurately identifies the semantic concept (the category and sentiment) even when it fails to replicate the exact syntactic boundaries (the span) of the human annotation.

Strategy	Triplet F1	ACSA F1	ACSA Prec.	ACSA Rec.	Sent. Acc.	Validity
A: Sentiment Only	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.8784	100%
B: Zero-Shot Structured	0.1053	0.5263	0.4639	0.6081	N/A	100%
C: Few-Shot (k=3)	0.0585	0.5380	0.4742	0.6216	N/A	100%

Table 1: Performance comparison across prompting strategies (N=63). Data originally collected in the pilot study by Småland 2025.

4.5 Conclusion on Metrics

Based on these diagnostic findings, this project suggests a preference to reject “Strict Span Extraction” as a primary success metric for the final thesis, as the ground truth itself is inherently noisy at the span level. Instead, future experiments could pivot to Aspect Category Sentiment Analysis (ACSA). This approach measures the model’s ability to correctly identify the category and sentiment tuple, aligning with the high-reliability components ($\kappa = 0.93$) of the human baseline.

5 Methodology

5.1 Research Methodology

To ensure a comprehensive and reproducible mapping of the state-of-the-art, this study employs a **Structured Literature Review (SLR)**. The review process was executed in strict accordance with the guidelines for computer science researchers proposed by Kofod-Petersen 2018, structured into three distinct phases:

1. **Planning:** Defining the review protocol, specifying research questions (Section 1.5), and establishing inclusion/exclusion criteria to minimize selection bias.
2. **Conducting:** Executing the search strategy across digital libraries, performing multi-stage screening (Title/Abstract → Full Text), and extracting data regarding architectural choices and performance metrics.
3. **Reporting:** Synthesizing the findings to identify research gaps (Chapter 3) and informing the experimental design (Chapter 8).

This rigorous approach is supplemented by targeted “snowballing” (following citations in primary studies) to capture recent high-impact works in the rapidly evolving field of Generative AI that may not yet be indexed in standard taxonomies.

5.1.1 Adapted Search Strategy: The Two-Stream Approach

Given the dual nature of the research objective—requiring both advanced technical methodology and domain-specific application—this project adapts the standard single-query protocol into a **Two-Stream Search Strategy**. Two complementary “bins” of queries were employed to ensure coverage of both the theoretical and practical dimensions:

- **Stream A: “Structure-Focused”**
This stream targets the theoretical frontier of the field. It emphasizes query terms related to *Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis*, *Stance Detection*, and *Generative Architectures* (e.g., “Seq2Seq”, “Prompting”) to identify the most capable models regardless of the language they were originally tested on.
- **Stream B: “Resource-Focused”**
This stream targets the operational constraints of the domain. It utilizes query terms related to *Low-Resource Settings*, *Nordic Languages*, and *Public Sector/Bureaucratic Text* to identify methods specifically proven to work in data-scarce environments.

5.2 Search Execution

5.2.1 Data Sources

To ensure high scientific quality, searches were restricted to peer-reviewed archives. The primary searches were executed in:

- **ACM Digital Library** (Computer Science focus)
- **IEEE Xplore** (Engineering and Systems focus)
- **ACL Anthology** (Computational Linguistics focus)

Two-Stream Search Strategy

Figure 2: Conceptual mapping of the Two-Stream Search Strategy, illustrating the intersection between structural methodology and domain constraints.

5.2.2 Term Selection and Strategy

In order to execute the Two-Stream strategy defined above, key terms were selected and grouped based on their relevance to the research questions. The boolean construction of these terms is detailed in Figure 2.

Table 2: Search term categories and corresponding core strings used in the Structured Literature Review

Category	Core search strings
Method / Task	ABSA, Aspect-Based Sentiment, Stance Detection, Target-Sentiment
Model / Architecture	LLM, Transformer, Chain-of-Thought, BERT, Encoder
Document Characteristics	Long Document, Legal, Policy, Bureaucratic, Formal Text, Multi-aspect
Domain / Language / Resource setting	Public Sector, Municipality, E-Government, Norwegian, Low-Resource Language

5.2.3 Initial Search Output

The combined queries yielded $N = 789$ records, reflecting considerable terminological and methodological overlap across domains involving transformer-based models, sentiment analysis, and stance detection.

5.2.4 Deduplication Procedure

All records were exported to Zotero and automatically screened for duplicates. Duplicate items (arising particularly from ACM/ACL overlap) were removed in accordance with the recommendation by Kofod-Petersen 2018 that duplicate removal constitutes the first exclusion step in a systematic review. The candidate set after deduplication and built-in temporal and document-type filtering is therefore $N = 758$.

5.2.5 Temporal Filtering

Given that transformer-based approaches first became dominant after the introduction by Vaswani et al. 2017 as seen in Section 2.3.2 (and most seminal papers are after 2020), with the addition that the review focuses specifically on contemporary LLM-based techniques, the dataset was restricted to publications from 2020–2025. This was applied as part of the digital library search query filters (ACM/IEEE/ACL support year-limit filters)

5.2.6 Document-Type Filtering

In line with common SLR guidelines, only peer-reviewed journal articles and full conference papers were retained. Short papers, posters, workshop papers without full review, extended abstracts, tutorials and theses were excluded. This step is also baked into the initial search parameters, implemented via built-in filtering options for publication venue/type in ACM and IEEE; ACL Anthology requires manual filtering which was done with a python script using a parser for BibTeX. Outliers were processed manually by verifying type of document.

5.2.7 Selection of Primary Studies

Following the deduplication and initial filtering, the candidate set ($N = 758$) underwent a rigorous multi-stage screening process to identify primary studies relevant to the research questions. In accordance with Kofod-Petersen’s guidelines for systematic reviews in computer science Kofod-Petersen 2018, this process was divided into two phases: (1) Title and Abstract Screening, and (2) Full-Text Quality Assessment.

Phase 1: Title and Abstract Screening The first phase aimed to remove irrelevant studies based on high-level exclusion criteria, as shown in Table 3. Given the dual nature of the research objective, requiring both advanced technical methodology and domain-specific application, a “Two-Stream” inclusion strategy was chosen to avoid a strict but deficient intersection between the two. A study was retained if it satisfied the criteria for *either* of the following bins:

- **Bin A (Methodological Relevance):** Studies proposing advanced NLP architectures (e.g., Large Language Models, Chain-of-Thought prompting, Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning) capable of handling long-context, hierarchical, or complex document structures, regardless of the original domain (e.g., legal or medical texts).
- **Bin B (Domain Relevance):** Studies explicitly applying NLP techniques to public sector, e-government, or civic engagement contexts, or addressing low-resource language challenges (e.g., Norwegian/Nordic), even if using standard architectures.

Studies focused exclusively on short-text sentiment (e.g., Twitter, product reviews) or non-text modalities were excluded unless they demonstrated explicit cross-domain transferability. This screening phase resulted in a set of $N = 160$ potentially relevant papers.

Table 3: Exclusion criteria applied during screening

EC	Criterion and triggering examples
EC1	Wrong modality – e.g., Image, Audio, Video, Multimodal, Speech Recognition (unless text is also analysed)
EC2	Irrelevant domain – e.g., Twitter/Tweet, Restaurant, Yelp, E-commerce, Stock Market, Hate Speech, Misinformation, News
EC3	Outdated/non-transformer method – e.g., LSTM, CNN, RNN, SVM, Naive Bayes, Lexicon-based (unless explicitly combined with transformers/LLMs)
EC4	Wrong primary task – e.g., Translation, Summarization (without sentiment/stance), Question Answering (without stance)
EC5	Non-primary material – e.g., Index, TOC, Proceedings, Front Matter, Program

Phase 2: Full-Text Quality Assessment The remaining 160 papers are subjected to a full-text review to assess their methodological rigor and relevance. In this ongoing phase, studies are evaluated against specific Quality Criteria (QC) to ensure the validity of the final corpus (Kofod-Petersen 2018):

- QC1 Is there a clear statement of the research aim?
- QC2 Does the study present empirical results on a reproducible dataset or clearly defined case study?
- QC3 For Methodological papers (Bin A): Is the proposed architecture evaluated against relevant baselines?
- QC4 For Domain papers (Bin B): Does the study provide actionable insights into the specific challenges of bureaucratic or civic text?

Only studies scoring above the threshold on these criteria will be included in the final data synthesis.

5.2.8 Data Extraction Strategy

For the final set of included studies, data is extracted using a predefined form to answer the research questions. The extraction focuses on: (1) The specific NLP task formulation (e.g., ABSA, Stance Detection); (2) The model architecture used (e.g., BERT-based vs. Generative LLM); (3) Strategies for handling data scarcity; and (4) Reported performance metrics.

Figure 3: PRISMA flow diagram detailing the selection process of primary studies.

6 Results

6.1 Overview of Included Studies

The Structured Literature Review (SLR) process resulted in the selection of $N = 26$ primary studies. The selected corpus is predominantly recent, with over half of the studies (65%) published between 2023 and 2025, reflecting the rapid emergence of Large Language Models (LLMs) in this domain.

The analysis reveals three dominant methodological clusters relevant to the Oslo Municipality use case: (1) **Generative Paradigms** that reformulate ABSA as a text generation task; (2) **Structure-Aware Architectures** that utilize graph neural networks to parse complex syntax; and (3) **Label-Efficient Adaptation** strategies for low-resource domains.

6.2 The Paradigm Shift: From Classification to Generation

A primary finding of the SLR is the decisive shift in the state-of-the-art (SOTA) from discriminative classifiers (e.g., BERT + Softmax) to generative frameworks (e.g., T5, GPT). This trend is driven by the ability of generative models to produce structured output (tuples) in a single pass.

6.2.1 Generative ABSA for Tuple Extraction

Traditional methods often treat aspect extraction and sentiment classification as separate pipelined tasks, leading to cascading errors. Hosseini-Asl et al. 2022 demonstrate that reformulating Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) as a sequence-to-sequence generation task allows a single model to output structured tuples (e.g., [Aspect, Sentiment]) directly.

This perspective is extended by Z. Wang et al. 2024, who introduce *Unified ABSA*. Their method employs multi-task instruction tuning to decouple annotations, enabling knowledge transfer across task formulations. Furthermore, Wu et al. 2025 push this boundary by combining text generation with *Multi-View Contrastive Learning*, improving the extraction of sentiment triplets in ambiguous contexts.

Key Finding: Generative ABSA dominates the SOTA because it treats sentiment analysis as structured generation rather than token tagging. This naturally scales to the complex sentiment structures (Aspect, Category, Polarity) required by the complexity we find in the municipality documents.

6.2.2 Synthetic Data and Self-Training

Addressing the “Cold Start” problem (which relates to RQ2), recent works leverage the generative capabilities of LLMs to synthesize training data. However, the SLR identifies two competing strategies for this synthesis:

- **Text-to-Label:** Hongling Xu et al. 2025 propose *DS²-ABSA*, which generates diverse training texts first and then prompts an LLM to label them.
- **Label-to-Text (Inverse Generation):** A. Wang et al. 2023 argue that rewriting texts limits semantic diversity. They propose a *Generative Data Augmentation* approach where the model first samples a valid sentiment tuple (e.g., Category: Noise, Polarity: Negative) and then trains a “Quads-to-Text” model to generate the corresponding sentence. This ensures perfect alignment between the generated text and the sentiment label, eliminating the noise often found in standard pseudo-labeling.

These findings suggest that for Norwegian, where data quality is paramount, the “Label-to-Text” approach may provide a more robust ground truth than simple text augmentation.

6.3 Structure-Aware Architectures for Complex Syntax

While generative models excel at semantic coherence, graph-based methods show that they remain superior for handling the complex syntactic dependencies typical of bureaucratic text (“Kansellistol”). However good they are, they pose challenges in their construction complexity.

Zheng et al. 2025 propose **GT-AGCN**, a hybrid model integrating global semantics (via Transformers) with local syntax (via Graph Convolutional Networks). Their results show that explicitly modeling dependency trees significantly reduces “attention bias,” where models incorrectly associate sentiment words with the wrong aspect in long sentences.

Additionally, Shu et al. 2025 introduce a dual-channel architecture to mitigate semantic interference in multi-aspect sentences. Crucially, N. Yang et al. 2023 add an additional layer by modeling *affective dependencies*, or rather connections derived from external sentiment knowledge bases. This enriches the model’s ability to infer polarity in texts where sentiment is implicit or expressed via neutral surface forms.

Key Finding: Structure-aware methods excel in domains where sentiment is subtle, indirect, and embedded in complex sentence structures; precisely the linguistic characteristics of municipal hearings.

6.4 Low-Resource and Domain Adaptation

A critical challenge in applying these methods to Norwegian municipal documents is the absence of domain-specific annotated data. The SLR identified specific architectures designed to bridge this gap.

- **DomBERT:** Hu Xu et al. 2020 demonstrate that domain-adaptive pretraining (continuing to train BERT on raw domain text) significantly boosts performance when in-domain data is small. This is highly relevant for “Kansellistol” documents, which pose the hardest problems.
- **SetFitQuad:** Chuang and Lin 2025 introduce a lightweight few-shot framework that combines sentence-level embeddings with syntactic heuristics. It achieves competitive performance with a fraction of the computational cost of massive generative models.
- **Legal NLP Mapping:** Quevedo et al. 2024 confirm that general-purpose models consistently underperform on administrative texts, validating the need for the specialized adaptation strategies identified above.

6.5 Summary of Findings

The SLR results suggest a hybrid path forward. While **Generative Models** offer the most flexible path for tuple extraction (Z. Wang et al. 2024), they may require **Structural Augmentation** to handle the syntactic density of bureaucratic Norwegian (Zheng et al. 2025). Furthermore, **Inverse Generative Augmentation** (A. Wang et al. 2023) appears to be the most promising method for constructing a high-fidelity synthetic dataset for the municipality.

7 Analysis and Discussion

7.1 Interpreting the SOTA for Bureaucratic Domains

The literature review in Chapter 6 established a clear trajectory in the field: the trend is moving away from token-classification towards generative architectures. While papers such as *DomBERT* and *DS²-ABSA* demonstrate the potential for low-resource adaptation, the pilot study in Chapter 4 revealed a potential critical gap: these methods are predominantly benchmarked on datasets with explicit sentiment targets, such as consumer product reviews. The adaptability and transferability of these strategies is the crux of the matter.

When applied to Norwegian bureaucratic text, the inherent ambiguity of “aspect boundaries” creates a performance ceiling for standard extraction methods. Pilot data from Småland 2025 in Section 4 showed that even capable generative models struggle to agree with human annotators on exact spans (Strict F1 \approx 0.10). This disparity suggests that the “State of the Art” for municipalities is not merely a question of model architecture (e.g., T5 vs. BERT), but fundamentally a question of task formulation (ACSA vs. ABSA) and the underlying strategies for prompting.

7.2 Implications for the AI Factory Pipeline

The transition from Strict ABSA to Aspect Category Sentiment Analysis (ACSA) has direct operational implications for Oslo Municipality’s “AI Factory” initiative. The Municipality’s primary objective should be decision support; more specifically, quantifying the volume of support or opposition toward specific policy themes (e.g., “Noise,” “Green Space”).

The pilot results demonstrate that while Large Language Models struggle to replicate exact human span annotations, they are significantly more capable of identifying the correct semantic category and sentiment (ACSA F1 \approx 0.53). For a decision-support system, the *category* is the actionable signal; the *span* is acting as supporting evidence.

Therefore, this project recommends that future pipelines in the AI Factory should **decouple** these two tasks, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Proposed AI Factory pipeline decoupling. The workflow separates statistical aggregation (Green) from explainability features (Orange) to mitigate span ambiguity errors.

The system should prioritize categorization for statistical aggregation, while treating extracted text spans as “soft evidence” for explainability (i.e., highlighting relevant text regions) rather than as rigid database keys. This approach bypasses the inherent ambiguity of bureaucratic text boundaries while preserving the analytical value for case handlers.

7.3 Synthesis of Research Questions

7.3.1 RQ1: The Methodological Landscape

The state-of-the-art methods for aspect extraction are increasingly Generative and Structure-Aware. Our review indicates that for complex documents, simple BERT classifiers are insufficient because they lack the ability to model long-range dependencies and implicit sentiment. However, the pi-

lot study demonstrates that “out-of-the-box” cutting-edge generative models like Gemini 2.5 Pro still struggle with strict span extraction in Norwegian. This implies that SOTA methods must be adapted with In-Context Learning or techniques adjacent to fine-tuning, in order to perform reliably in this specific domain.

7.3.2 RQ2: Ground Truth Construction

The pilot study briefs us with an explicit answer regarding the construction of a reliable ground truth. The low inter-annotator agreement for spans ($\kappa = 0.21$) proves that defining “Ground Truth” as “exact word boundaries” is methodologically flawed for municipal hearings. On the other hand, the high agreement for categories ($\kappa = 0.93$) indicates that the ontology is robust. Therefore, a reliable ground truth for Oslo Municipality should be constructed at the Category-Sentiment level. Future annotation efforts should focus on verifying the *existence* of a sentiment within a text segment, rather than debating the precise start and end indices of the phrase.

7.3.3 RQ3: Practical Feasibility

The results indicate that modern LLM-based pipelines are highly feasible for quantifying positions (ACSA F1 ≈ 0.53), even in a zero-shot setting. If we consider the tendency of over-eagerness to classify by the LLMs, this can be improved further with restrictive prompting. However, they are currently not feasible for the perfect extraction of aspect terms without further optimization. For the “AI Factory,” this means a production pipeline can reliably produce indicative statistics (e.g., “70% of submissions oppose the height”) but should present extracted text spans as supporting citations with a confidence disclaimer, rather than as absolute truth.

7.4 Summary

This analysis reconciles the theoretical potential of Generative AI with the practical constraints of Norwegian bureaucratic text. While the literature review (RQ1) points toward generative architectures, the pilot study (RQ2) confirms that “Strict Extraction” is a flawed objective due to inherent boundary ambiguity. Consequently, the practical feasibility of the system (RQ3) depends on a strategic pivot to Aspect Category Sentiment Analysis (ACSA). This insight forms the basis for the Master’s Thesis proposal outlined in Chapter 8.

8 Conclusion and Future Work

8.1 Conclusion

This specialization project investigated the feasibility of automating Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) for the complex, low-resource domain of Norwegian municipal case/“hearing” document processing. Through a Structured Literature Review (SLR) covering $N = 26$ primary studies, we identified a paradigm shift in the field from discriminative token classification to Generative AI and Structure-Aware architectures.

Meanwhile, a pilot study on $N = 63$ hearing sentences provided critical (although still rocky) empirical evidence of a “Span Ambiguity Gap.” While strict span extraction proved unreliable ($\kappa = 0.21$, F1 ≈ 0.10) due to the inherent “fuzziness” of bureaucratic phrasing, semantic categorization remained robust ($\kappa = 0.93$, F1 ≈ 0.53). Consequently, we conclude that a “naive” extraction pipeline is insufficient for the AI Factory. To deliver actionable decision support, the subsequent Master’s Thesis benefits from a pivot from standard ABSA to **Aspect Category Sentiment Analysis (ACSA)**, leveraging generative models to bypass syntactic ambiguity while preserving semantic intent.

8.2 Contributions

This project makes three primary contributions to the field of Public Sector NLP:

1. **Methodological Mapping:** A Structured Literature Review identifying Generative-ACSA and Graph-based methods as the most viable architectures for low-resource, high-complexity domains.
2. **Domain Diagnostics:** Analysis of a pilot dataset, highlighting the “Span Ambiguity” phenomenon in Norwegian administrative text, challenging the utility of standard extraction metrics.
3. **Strategic Pivot:** Evidence-based justification for shifting Oslo Municipality’s AI strategy from fine-grained extraction to robust categorization, ensuring higher reliability for decision-makers.

8.3 Future Work: Master’s Thesis Proposal

Based on the findings above, the Master’s Thesis will operationalize the “Generative ACSA” approach. The following experimental plan outlines the roadmap for the next semester.

8.4 Experimental Plan

8.4.1 Overview and Data Strategy

The Master’s Thesis will examine how Aspect-Category Sentiment Analysis (ACSA) can be operationalized in a low-resource environment to support the Municipality’s “AI Factory.” To address the “Cold Start” problem identified in Section 3.1, the data strategy can employ a **Teacher-Student framework** utilizing synthetic data generation.

The dataset construction will follow a two-tiered approach designed to bridge the gap between unstructured text and structured database tuples:

- **Gold Standard Test Set (Manual):** A small, high-quality corpus of municipal hearing documents will be manually annotated by the author. This serves as the ground truth for evaluation. Annotations will be strictly formatted as ACSA tuples to ensure database compatibility:

(Text Segment, Category, Polarity)

- **Silver Training Set (Synthetic):** To overcome data scarcity, we will implement the “Label-to-Text” (Inverse Generation) strategy identified in Section 6.2.2. A Large Language Model (e.g., GPT-4 or Llama 3) will serve as the “Teacher,” prompted to generate synthetic municipal texts conditioned on specific aspect-sentiment tuples (e.g., *Generate a formal objection regarding ‘Building Height’ with ‘Negative’ polarity*). This allows us to train smaller, sovereign models on a statistically significant volume of data without manual labeling costs.

8.4.2 Research Questions for the Thesis

The experiments are designed to compare naive baselines against a domain-adapted architecture, specifically addressing the following questions:

- **RQ1 (The Baseline):** How effectively can standard Norwegian discriminative models (e.g., NorBERT) perform ACSA when trained exclusively on limited manually annotated data?

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- **RQ2 (The Teacher):** To what extent can zero-shot Large Language Models (e.g., GPT-4, Llama 3) correctly extract ACSA tuples without task-specific training?
 - **RQ3 (The Synthesis):** Can a **Structure-Aware “Student” model** trained on **synthetically generated data** (Inverse Generation) outperform the baseline in RQ1 and approximate the performance of the teacher in RQ2?

8.4.3 Proposed Methodological Framework

The experiments are organized into a “Champion vs. Challenger” design, testing whether the combination of specialized architecture and synthetic data yields the optimal balance of performance and resource efficiency.

Condition A: Pretrained Transformer Baseline (Discriminative)

A standard supervised classifier will be implemented using a pretrained Norwegian encoder (NorBERT or NB-BERT) (Kummervold et al. 2021;Kutuzov et al. 2021), fine-tuned only on the small manual dataset.

Purpose: Establishes the “Cold Start” performance floor, representing the status quo of applying standard NLP to low-resource Norwegian domains.

Condition B: Generative Instruction-Tuned Model (The Teacher)

Following the SLR’s identification of generative models as the current SOTA, this condition evaluates a Large Language Model (e.g., GPT-4o or Llama-3) in a zero-shot prompt-based formulation.

Purpose: Serves as the high-capacity “Teacher” benchmark. While powerful, this approach is treated as computationally expensive and potentially non-compliant with strict data sovereignty requirements, motivating the need for Condition C.

Condition C: Structure-Aware Model + Synthetic Augmentation (The Solution)

This condition synthesizes the two primary findings of the Literature Review. It implements a lightweight **Structure-Aware architecture** (e.g., Graph Convolutional Network over dependency trees, as seen in GT-AGCN (Zheng et al. 2025)) trained on the **Synthetic “Silver” Dataset** generated by Condition B.

Rationale: This tests the hypothesis that explicitly modeling bureaucratic syntax (via graphs) combined with overcoming data scarcity (via synthetic augmentation) provides the most robust solution for the Municipality.

8.4.4 Evaluation Strategy

To ensure the output is viable for the AI Factory’s database systems, models will be evaluated using a 5-fold cross-validation setup with metrics focused on structured information retrieval:

- **Primary:** Tuple Exact-Match Macro-F1 (measuring the correct retrieval of the full (Category, Polarity) pair).
- **Secondary:** Per-Category F1 (to detect bias against rare policy themes).
- **Ablation Study:** Measuring performance scaling as the volume of synthetic training data increases (e.g., $N = 500$ vs. $N = 5000$).

8.5 Summary

This experimental design ensures coherence with the SLR findings, directly addresses the “Span Ambiguity” constraint, and provides a clear path toward a deployable solution for Oslo Municipality’s AI Factory.

Bibliography

- Brown, Tom B. et al. (2020). 'Language models are few-shot learners'. In: *Proceedings of the 34th International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems*. NIPS '20. Vancouver, BC, Canada: Curran Associates Inc. ISBN: 9781713829546.
- Chalkidis, Ilias, Ion Androutsopoulos and Nikolaos Aletras (July 2019). 'Neural Legal Judgment Prediction in English'. In: *Proceedings of the 57th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*. Ed. by Anna Korhonen, David Traum and Lluís Màrquez. Florence, Italy: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 4317–4323. DOI: 10.18653/v1/P19-1424. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/P19-1424/>.
- Chuang, Hsiu-Min and Jhe-Kuan Lin (Aug. 2025). 'SetFitQuad: A Few-Shot Framework for Aspect Sentiment Quad Prediction With Sampling Strategies'. In: *IEEE Access* 13, pp. 146204–146217. ISSN: 2169-3536. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3600351.
- Devlin, Jacob et al. (June 2019). 'BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding'. In: *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, Volume 1 (Long and Short Papers)*. Ed. by Jill Burstein, Christy Doran and Thamar Solorio. Minneapolis, Minnesota: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 4171–4186. DOI: 10.18653/v1/N19-1423. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/N19-1423/>.
- Ding, Ning et al. (Mar. 2023). 'Parameter-efficient fine-tuning of large-scale pre-trained language models'. In: *Nature Machine Intelligence* 5, pp. 1–16. DOI: 10.1038/s42256-023-00626-4.
- Hearst, Marti A. (1999). 'Untangling text data mining'. In: *Proceedings of the 37th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics on Computational Linguistics*. ACL '99. College Park, Maryland: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 3–10. ISBN: 1558606093. DOI: 10.3115/1034678.1034679. URL: <https://doi.org/10.3115/1034678.1034679>.
- Hedderich, Michael A. et al. (June 2021). 'A Survey on Recent Approaches for Natural Language Processing in Low-Resource Scenarios'. In: *Proceedings of the 2021 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies*. Ed. by Kristina Toutanova et al. Online: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 2545–2568. DOI: 10.18653/v1/2021.naacl-main.201. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/2021.naacl-main.201/>.
- Hochreiter, Sepp and Jürgen Schmidhuber (Nov. 1997). 'Long Short-Term Memory'. In: *Neural Comput.* 9.8, pp. 1735–1780. ISSN: 0899-7667. DOI: 10.1162/neco.1997.9.8.1735. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1162/neco.1997.9.8.1735>.
- Hosseini-Asl, Ehsan, Wenhao Liu and Caiming Xiong (July 2022). 'A Generative Language Model for Few-shot Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis'. In: *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: NAACL 2022*. Ed. by Marine Carpuat, Marie-Catherine de Marneffe and Ivan Vladimir Meza Ruiz. Seattle, United States: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 770–787. DOI: 10.18653/v1/2022.findings-naacl.58. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/2022.findings-naacl.58/>.
- Hu, Edward J. et al. (2021). *LoRA: Low-Rank Adaptation of Large Language Models*. arXiv: 2106.09685 [cs.CL]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2106.09685>.
- Hu, Minqing and Bing Liu (2004). 'Mining and summarizing customer reviews'. In: *Proceedings of the Tenth ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*. KDD '04. Seattle, WA, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, pp. 168–177. ISBN: 1581138881. DOI: 10.1145/1014052.1014073. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/1014052.1014073>.
- Kofod-Petersen, Anders (2018). *How to do a Structured Literature Review in computer science*. Tech. rep. Norwegian University of Science and Technology.
- Kummervold, Per E et al. (May 2021). 'Operationalizing a National Digital Library: The Case for a Norwegian Transformer Model'. In: *Proceedings of the 23rd Nordic Conference on Computational Linguistics (NoDaLiDa)*. Ed. by Simon Dobnik and Lilja Øvrelid. Reykjavik, Iceland (Online): Linköping University Electronic Press, Sweden, pp. 20–29. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/2021.nodalida-main.3/>.
- Kutuzov, Andrey et al. (May 2021). 'Large-Scale Contextualised Language Modelling for Norwegian'. In: *Proceedings of the 23rd Nordic Conference on Computational Linguistics (NoDaLiDa)*. Ed. by Simon Dobnik and Lilja Øvrelid. Reykjavik, Iceland (Online): Linköping University Electronic Press, Sweden, pp. 30–40. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/2021.nodalida-main.4/>.

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- Li, Zhuoyan et al. (Dec. 2023). ‘Synthetic Data Generation with Large Language Models for Text Classification: Potential and Limitations’. In: *Proceedings of the 2023 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*. Ed. by Houda Bouamor, Juan Pino and Kalika Bali. Singapore: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 10443–10461. DOI: 10.18653/v1/2023.emnlp-main.647. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/2023.emnlp-main.647/>.
- Liu, Bing (May 2012). ‘Sentiment Analysis and Opinion Mining’. In: *Synthesis Lectures on Human Language Technologies* 5.1, pp. 1–167. DOI: 10.2200/s00416ed1v01y201204hlt016. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2200/S00416ED1V01Y201204HLT016>.
- NorwAI et al. (2024). *NorwAI/NorwAI-Mistral-7B*. <https://huggingface.co/NorwAI/NorwAI-Mistral-7B>. Hugging Face Model Card. Accessed on [Current Date].
- NorwAI (Norwegian Research Center for AI Innovation) (2023-2024). *NorLLM: A Guide to NorwAI’s work on Large Language Models in Norwegian*. <https://www.ntnu.edu/norllm/>. Accessed on: 06.12.25.
- OpenAI (Nov. 2022). *Introducing ChatGPT*. <https://openai.com/index/chatgpt/>. Accessed: YYYY-MM-DD.
- Pan, Sinno Jialin and Qiang Yang (Oct. 2010). ‘A Survey on Transfer Learning’. In: *IEEE Trans. on Knowl. and Data Eng.* 22.10, pp. 1345–1359. ISSN: 1041-4347. DOI: 10.1109/TKDE.2009.191. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TKDE.2009.191>.
- Pang, Bo and Lillian Lee (Jan. 2008). ‘Opinion Mining and Sentiment Analysis’. In: *Found. Trends Inf. Retr.* 2.1–2, pp. 1–135. ISSN: 1554-0669. DOI: 10.1561/1500000011. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1561/1500000011>.
- Pang, Bo, Lillian Lee and Shivakumar Vaithyanathan (July 2002). ‘Thumbs up? Sentiment Classification using Machine Learning Techniques’. In: *Proceedings of the 2002 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP 2002)*. Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 79–86. DOI: 10.3115/1118693.1118704. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/W02-1011/>.
- Pontiki, Maria et al. (Aug. 2014). ‘SemEval-2014 Task 4: Aspect Based Sentiment Analysis’. In: *Proceedings of the 8th International Workshop on Semantic Evaluation (SemEval 2014)*. Ed. by Preslav Nakov and Torsten Zesch. Dublin, Ireland: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 27–35. DOI: 10.3115/v1/S14-2004. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/S14-2004/>.
- Quevedo, Ernesto et al. (2024). ‘Legal Natural Language Processing From 2015 to 2022: A Comprehensive Systematic Mapping Study of Advances and Applications’. In: *IEEE Access* 12, pp. 145286–145317. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3333946.
- Radford, Alec and Karthik Narasimhan (2018). *Improving Language Understanding by Generative Pre-Training*. URL: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:49313245>.
- Shu, Wanneng, Cao Zhai and Ke Yu (Dec. 2025). ‘DAGCN: Dual-Channel and Aspect-Aware Graph Convolutional Network for Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis in Computational Social Systems’. In: *IEEE Transactions on Computational Social Systems* 12.6, pp. 5405–5415. ISSN: 2329-924X. DOI: 10.1109/TCSS.2024.3418472.
- Småland, Sebastian (Nov. 2025). *A Comparative Study of Prompting Strategies for Zero-Shot Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis*. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17867355. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17867355>.
- Soni, Piyush Kumar and Radhakrishna Rambola (2022). ‘A Survey on Implicit Aspect Detection for Sentiment Analysis: Terminology, Issues, and Scope’. In: *IEEE Access* 10, pp. 63932–63957. ISSN: 2169-3536. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3183205.
- Tang, Duyu, Bing Qin and Ting Liu (Nov. 2016). ‘Aspect Level Sentiment Classification with Deep Memory Network’. In: *Proceedings of the 2016 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*. Ed. by Jian Su, Kevin Duh and Xavier Carreras. Austin, Texas: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 214–224. DOI: 10.18653/v1/D16-1021. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/D16-1021/>.
- Turney, Peter (July 2002). ‘Thumbs Up or Thumbs Down? Semantic Orientation Applied to Unsupervised Classification of Reviews’. In: *Proceedings of the 40th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*. Ed. by Pierre Isabelle, Eugene Charniak and Dekang Lin. Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, USA: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 417–424. DOI: 10.3115/1073083.1073153. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/P02-1053/>.
- Vaswani, Ashish et al. (2017). ‘Attention is all you need’. In: *Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems. NIPS’17*. Long Beach, California, USA: Curran Associates Inc., pp. 6000–6010. ISBN: 9781510860964.
-

-
- Wang, An et al. (July 2023). ‘Generative Data Augmentation for Aspect Sentiment Quad Prediction’. In: *Proceedings of the 12th Joint Conference on Lexical and Computational Semantics (*SEM 2023)*. Ed. by Alexis Palmer and Jose Camacho-collados. Toronto, Canada: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 128–140. DOI: 10.18653/v1/2023.starsem-1.12. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/2023.starsem-1.12/>.
- Wang, Zengzhi, Rui Xia and Jianfei Yu (2024). ‘Unified ABSA via Annotation-Decoupled Multi-Task Instruction Tuning’. In: *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* 36.11, pp. 7242–7254. DOI: 10.1109/TKDE.2024.3392836.
- Wei, Jason et al. (2022). *Finetuned Language Models Are Zero-Shot Learners*. arXiv: 2109.01652 [cs.CL]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2109.01652>.
- Wiebe, Janyce M., Rebecca F. Bruce and Thomas P. O’Hara (June 1999). ‘Development and Use of a Gold-Standard Data Set for Subjectivity Classifications’. In: *Proceedings of the 37th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*. College Park, Maryland, USA: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 246–253. DOI: 10.3115/1034678.1034721. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/P99-1032/>.
- Wu, Wenfang et al. (2025). ‘Sentiment Triplet Extraction With Multi-View Contrastive Learning’. In: *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing* 16.3, pp. 1526–1542. DOI: 10.1109/TAFFC.2024.3521608.
- Xu, Hongling et al. (July 2025). ‘DS²-ABSA: Dual-Stream Data Synthesis with Label Refinement for Few-Shot Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis’. In: *Proceedings of the 63rd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers)*. Ed. by Wanxiang Che et al. Vienna, Austria: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 15460–15478. ISBN: 979-8-89176-251-0. DOI: 10.18653/v1/2025.acl-long.752. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/2025.acl-long.752/>.
- Xu, Hu et al. (Nov. 2020). ‘DombERT: Domain-oriented Language Model for Aspect-based Sentiment Analysis’. In: *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: EMNLP 2020*. Ed. by Trevor Cohn, Yulan He and Yang Liu. Online: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 1725–1731. DOI: 10.18653/v1/2020.findings-emnlp.156. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/2020.findings-emnlp.156/>.
- Yan, Hang et al. (Aug. 2021). ‘A Unified Generative Framework for Aspect-based Sentiment Analysis’. In: *Proceedings of the 59th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics and the 11th International Joint Conference on Natural Language Processing (Volume 1: Long Papers)*. Ed. by Chengqing Zong et al. Online: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 2416–2429. DOI: 10.18653/v1/2021.acl-long.188. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/2021.acl-long.188/>.
- Yang, Ning, Xiaoge Li and Xiangpeng Du (July 2023). ‘Aspect-level Sentiment Analysis Based on Semantic and Affective Dependency Enhancement’. In: *2023 42nd Chinese Control Conference (CCC)*, pp. 8780–8785. DOI: 10.23919/CCC58697.2023.10240137.
- Zhang, Wenxuan et al. (Nov. 2021). ‘Aspect Sentiment Quad Prediction as Paraphrase Generation’. In: *Proceedings of the 2021 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*. Ed. by Marie-Francine Moens et al. Online and Punta Cana, Dominican Republic: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 9209–9219. DOI: 10.18653/v1/2021.emnlp-main.726. URL: <https://aclanthology.org/2021.emnlp-main.726/>.
- Zhang, Xue et al. (2021). ‘Automated Context-Aware Phrase Mining from Text Corpora’. In: *Database Systems for Advanced Applications: 26th International Conference, DASFAA 2021, Taipei, Taiwan, April 11–14, 2021, Proceedings, Part II*. Taipei, Taiwan: Springer-Verlag, pp. 20–36. ISBN: 978-3-030-73196-0. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-73197-7_2. URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-73197-7_2.
- Zheng, Wenjun et al. (2025). ‘GT-AGCN: Integrating Global Semantics and Local Syntax for Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis’. In: *IEEE Transactions on Computational Social Systems*, pp. 1–17. ISSN: 2329-924X. DOI: 10.1109/TCSS.2025.3588104.